

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF THE U.S. EDUCATION SYSTEM IN DIRECTING YOUNG PEOPLE TO PROFESSIONS

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Abstract: In this article, the conditions created for the education of young people and their place in the life of young people, and the attention paid to the education of young generations in the development of any society and their rise to the top, are highlighted.

Key words: developed countries, kindergarten, elementary school, public education, American colloquial speech, school, education, training courses, program

Introduction:

Higher education institutions vary greatly in terms of the quality of education. The 8 Ivy League universities are among the most prestigious universities in the United States and around the world. At about age 5, American children go to elementary school (English: elementary school), grade zero (German: kindergarten). In many states, zero grade is optional.

However, almost all American children attend kindergarten. Although Kindergarten literally means "kindergarten" in German, in the United States, kindergartens exist separately and are literally called preschools. Elementary school lasts until the fifth or sixth grade (depending on the school district), after which the student goes to middle school (English: middle school), ending with the eighth or ninth grade, respectively.

High school (English: highschool) is grades nine through twelfth, so Americans usually finish high school at age 18. Those with a high school diploma can attend community colleges. In statistics, such educational institutions are called two-year colleges (two-year colleges), other names are also widespread: English: community college, small college, technical college or city college. These institutions give a scientific degree after two years of study (English: associate's degree).

Another option for continuing your education is to attend a college or university, where you can usually earn a bachelor's degree in four years. Those with a bachelor's degree can further study for a master's degree (2-3 years) or a PhD (3 years or more). Specially accredited faculties and universities (post-graduate schools) that require special preparation at the undergraduate level for

admission award the degrees of doctor of medical sciences and doctor of jurisprudence.

Free public schools are primarily governed by democratically elected school boards, each of which has jurisdiction over a school district, often (but not always) bounded by a county or city boundaries and includes one or more schools at each level. School boards determine school programs, hire teachers, and determine program funding.

Most of the children study in public schools. For example, in 2013, about 87 percent of school-age children were educated in free public schools, about 10 percent in private schools, and 3 percent at home. However, using a non-registered free school in the US is prohibited, even if it appears to be "premium". Many private fee-paying schools are religious. The most widespread network of Catholic schools established by Irish immigrants in the second half of the 19th century. There are other private schools, often very expensive and sometimes highly competitive, to prepare students for admission to prestigious universities.

Still others want to protect children from the drugs and crime that are problems in some schools. In many places, homeschooling parents form support groups, sometimes with different parents teaching different subjects. Many supplement their studies with distance learning programs and classes at local colleges. Despite the many problems in secondary education, higher education in the United States is considered one of the best in the world.

Higher education is usually obtained after 4-6 years of study at a college or university. In 2009, there were 4,352 institutions of higher education in the United States. In 2008, 36 percent of university graduates completed a four-year program (bachelor's degree) and 57 percent completed a six-year program (bachelor's + master's degree). In 2001, US universities had 515,000 international students out of a total of 17.5 million, 60% of whom were from Asia. Recently, education in private and state universities is becoming more and more expensive.

Annual tuition fees range from \$5,000 at State University to \$40,000 at Harvard, and while generous scholarships are awarded to poor students, they are often inadequate for middle-class students, who often lose much of their family income.

From 2002-2003 to the 2003-2004 academic year, tuition fees in public higher education institutions increased by 14 percent, and in private higher education institutions by 6 percent, which is more than the rate of inflation during the

same period. In American colloquial speech, all universities are usually called colleges (English: college), even though they are not colleges but universities.

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